

Study of the Effect of Anisotropic Metamaterials on Electromagnetic Wave Propagation in Cylindrical Waveguides

Zainab N. Mutashar

Department of Physics, Thi-Qar Directorate of Education, Iraq

Sura N. Tarrad ✉

Department of Physics, Divaniyah Directorate of Education, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Mutashar, Z.N., & Tarrad, S.N. (2024). Study of the Effect of Anisotropic Metamaterials on Electromagnetic Wave Propagation in Cylindrical Waveguides. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 219-232. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).17](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).17)

Abstract:

This research is centered on investigating electromagnetic wave propagation in metamaterials with anisotropic features. These metamaterials are distinguished from isotropic materials in regard to their effects on waves. Unlike single-negative materials (SNG), all modes propagate in reverse, then transform into forward propagation with positive energy flow at a certain frequency. In inhomogeneous waveguides, some higher modes show a continuous energy flow, either positive or negative, without transitions. The contrast factor is an important element in controlling the propagation properties within waveguides, as its modification affects

the propagation direction and other wave properties.

Keywords: *electromagnetic wave, metamaterials, anisotropic features, positive energy flow, contrast factor.*

Introduction

The metamaterials that have been used in different experiments are usually anisotropic in nature, and very difficult to prepare an isotropic left handed material. The characteristic peculiarity of the electromagnetic waves propagating in the uniaxial anisotropic LHM is significantly different than in isotropic left handed material. This distinction is especially evident in layered structures when propagating waves pass from one isotropic RHM into another anisotropic LHM and under these conditions of anomalous reflection or refraction are occur (Atakaramians, et al., 2012). Besides, in general case in uniaxial anisotropic media, the vectors \vec{E} , \vec{H} and \vec{k} cannot form a strictly left-handed orthogonal set of vectors and the directions of energy flow and the Poynting

vector \vec{S} cannot be in the exact opposite directions of wave vector (Engheta, 2003).

At the propagation of the electromagnetic waves along the interface in a circular structure, the surface electromagnetic waves can be formed. Surface modes can propagate in the region of frequencies where the permittivities of two connected media have the opposite signs, i.e. surface electromagnetic waves propagate at the interface between media with different “rightness”. Lately surface electromagnetic waves have attracted much interest in the context of nano-optics (Shen, & Wang, 2008), diverse applications and also can be used as a convenient tool for studying properties of the structured surfaces which is considered as optical metamaterials (Huang, Lu, & Sridhar, 2008). The characterized peculiarity of these waves are strong enhancement and spatial

confinement of the electromagnetic field of the waves near to the interface. In negative index material interest to surface wave is connected with the strong impact of the surface wave on the image resolution of a left handed material flat lens (Mickelson, 1993).

In this chapter, a mathematical modeling of complex media characterized by 3×3 anisotropic (uniaxial) tensors of permittivity and permeability parameters will be presented. We will solve the vector forms of free source Maxwell's equations to conclude the wave equations for the longitudinal components of the electric and magnetic fields. Then the wave equations are solved to determine the final formulas of the longitudinal fields. Wave equations are solved in the core and cladding regions with anisotropic SNG metamaterials. To obtain the dispersion relation and determine the constants resulting from the solutions of differential equations, the transverse fields' components should be calculated. The simulation is done by the Matlab environment and some results are confirmed using the COMSOL environment.

Maxwell's Equations in Vector Forms

The generally inhomogeneous nature suggests the waveguide supports hybrid electric HE_{mn} and hybrid magnetic EH_{mn} modes in which both the longitudinal (z -directed) electric and magnetic fields generally exist. Here, the indices m, n refer to the order of the mode's variation φ, ρ , respectively. In cylindrical coordinates, the electric and magnetic fields may be formed as the following:

$$\vec{E}(\rho, \varphi, z) = \vec{E}(\rho, \varphi)e^{-\gamma z} \quad (1a)$$

$$\vec{H}(\rho, \varphi, z) = \vec{H}(\rho, \varphi)e^{-\gamma z} \quad (1b)$$

where $\gamma = \alpha + ik_z$ is the longitudinal complex propagation constant. A time-harmonic behavior $e^{i\omega t}$ is assumed and suppressed throughout (Christensen, 2012). The transverse

decomposition of Maxwell's equations in a cylindrical coordinate system is used to construct the fields and dispersion relation of hybrid modes, where the general solution for the longitudinal components of the electric and magnetic fields in any region is obtained by the cylindrical wave equation in an unbounded cylindrically anisotropic medium (Mousa, & Shabat, 2015). The medium for the present discussion (in this research) will be regarded as homogeneous. However, the source free Maxwell's equations in vector notation take the forms

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -i\omega\vec{\mu}\vec{H} \quad (2a)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = i\omega\vec{\epsilon}\vec{E} \quad (2b)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{D} = 0 \quad (2c)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (2d)$$

Now, the electric and magnetic fields will be decomposed into the transverse and longitudinal components as: $\vec{E} = \vec{E}_t + \vec{E}_z$, $\vec{H} = \vec{H}_t + \vec{H}_z$. where t and z symbols refer to transverse and longitudinal. Using the field forms at Eqs.(1), the del operator may be reformed as $\vec{\nabla} = \vec{\nabla}_t + \hat{z} \partial/\partial z = \vec{\nabla}_t - \gamma\hat{z}$. More generally, both the dielectric permittivity and magnetic permeability can be anisotropic and are second order tensors that can be represented by 3×3 matrices. For axial symmetry of the medium, it is also clear that the permittivity and permeability tensors are uniaxial dyadic

$$\vec{\epsilon} = \vec{\epsilon}_t + \epsilon_z\hat{z}\hat{z} \quad (3a)$$

$$\vec{\mu} = \vec{\mu}_t + \mu_z\hat{z}\hat{z} \quad (3b)$$

Where

$$\vec{\varepsilon}_t = \varepsilon_x \hat{x}\hat{x} + \varepsilon_y \hat{y}\hat{y} \quad (3a)$$

$$\vec{\mu}_t = \mu_x \hat{x}\hat{x} + \mu_y \hat{y}\hat{y} \quad (3b)$$

are the transverse components of the permittivity and permeability tensors, while for cylindrically symmetric anisotropic medium for diagonal anisotropy, The permittivity and permeability tensors may be defined as

$$\vec{\varepsilon} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_\rho & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \varepsilon_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_\rho & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_\phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_z \end{bmatrix}$$

Using the above decompositions, Maxwell's equations will be

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t - \gamma \hat{z}) \times (\vec{E}_t + \hat{z}E_z) = -i\omega(\vec{\mu}_t + \mu_z \hat{z}\hat{z})(\vec{H}_t + \hat{z}H_z) \quad (4a)$$

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t - \gamma \hat{z}) \times (\vec{H}_t + \hat{z}H_z) = i\omega(\vec{\varepsilon}_t + \varepsilon_z \hat{z}\hat{z})(\vec{E}_t + \hat{z}E_z) \quad (4b)$$

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t - \gamma \hat{z}) \cdot (\vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t + \hat{z}\varepsilon_z E_z) = 0 \quad (4c)$$

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t - \gamma \hat{z}) \cdot (\vec{\mu}_t \vec{H}_t + \hat{z}\mu_z H_z) = 0 \quad (4d)$$

The cross and dot products in the last equations may be done and the results will be rearranged to get the following six equations

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t E_z + \gamma \vec{E}_t) \times \hat{z} = -i\omega \vec{\mu}_t \vec{H}_t \quad (5a)$$

$$(\vec{\nabla}_t H_z + \gamma \vec{H}_t) \times \hat{z} = i\omega \vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t \quad (5b)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_t \times \vec{E}_t = -i\omega \mu_z H_z \hat{z} \quad (5c)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_t \times \vec{H}_t = i\omega \varepsilon_z E_z \hat{z} \quad (5d)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_t \cdot \vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t = \gamma \varepsilon_z E_z \quad (5e)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_t \cdot \vec{\mu}_t \vec{H}_t = \gamma \mu_z H_z \quad (5f)$$

Multiplying Eq.(4.5b) by $\times \hat{z}$ and expanding the result yields

$$\hat{z} \times (\vec{\nabla}_t H_z \times \hat{z}) - \gamma \hat{z} \times (\hat{z} \times \vec{H}_t) = \hat{z} \times i\omega(\vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t)$$

which gives

$$\vec{\nabla}_t H_z + \gamma \vec{H}_t = \hat{z} \times (i\omega \vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t) \quad (6)$$

Using Eqs.(5a) and (6) with isolating $\hat{z} \times \vec{E}_t$ and \vec{H}_t to get:

$$\gamma \hat{z} \times \vec{E}_t = i\omega \vec{\mu}_t \vec{H}_t + \vec{\nabla}_t E_z \times \hat{z} \quad (7a)$$

$$\gamma \vec{H}_t = \hat{z} \times (i\omega \vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{E}_t) - \vec{\nabla}_t E_z \times \hat{z} \quad (7b)$$

The last equations may be solved simultaneously to get

$$\vec{E}_t = -\gamma(\vec{\gamma}_c)^{-1} \vec{\nabla}_t E_z + i\omega(\vec{\gamma}_c)^{-1} \hat{z} \times (\vec{\mu}_t \vec{\nabla}_t H_z) \quad (8a)$$

$$\vec{H}_t = -\gamma(\vec{\gamma}_c)^{-1} \vec{\nabla}_t E_z - i\omega(\vec{\gamma}_c)^{-1} \hat{z} \times (\vec{\varepsilon}_t \vec{\nabla}_t E_z) \quad (8b)$$

Where

$$\vec{\gamma}_c = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & a_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\vec{\gamma}_c)^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/a_2 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$a_1 = w^2 \varepsilon_\rho \mu_\phi - \gamma^2$$

$$a_2 = w^2 \varepsilon_\phi \mu_\rho - \gamma^2$$

The problem will analyze using the cylindrical forms of the fields \vec{E}_t, \vec{H}_t and the transverse operator $\vec{\nabla}_t$, which are defined as

$$\vec{\nabla}_t = \hat{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} + \frac{\hat{\phi}}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi}, \vec{E}_t = \hat{\rho} E_\rho + \hat{\phi} E_\phi, \vec{H}_t = \hat{\rho} H_\rho + \hat{\phi} H_\phi$$

Using these definitions, Eqs.(8) may be reformed in the matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_\rho \\ E_\phi \end{bmatrix} = -\gamma \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{a_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{a_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \\ \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} \end{bmatrix} + iw \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{a_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{a_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\mu_\phi}{\rho} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} \\ \mu_\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9a)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} H_\rho \\ H_\phi \end{bmatrix} = -\gamma \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{a_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{a_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \\ \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} \end{bmatrix} - iw \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{a_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{a_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\mu_\phi}{\rho} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} \\ \mu_\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9b)$$

Wave Equation in Anisotropic Media

The transverse electric and magnetic fields components may be deduced simply from Eqs.(4.9) to get

$$E_\rho = -\frac{\gamma}{a_1} \left(\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} + \frac{iw \mu_\phi}{\gamma \rho} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} \right) \quad (10a)$$

$$E_\phi = -\frac{\gamma}{a_2} \left(\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{iw \mu_\rho}{\gamma} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) \quad (10b)$$

$$H_\rho = -\frac{\gamma}{a_2} \left(\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} - \frac{iw \varepsilon_\phi}{\gamma \rho} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} \right) \quad (10c)$$

$$H_\phi = -\frac{\gamma}{a_1} \left(\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} + \frac{iw \varepsilon_\rho}{\gamma} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) \quad (10d)$$

This means that the expressions of the transverse field components may be calculated using Eqs.(4.10) provided the longitudinal components of the electric and magnetic fields, i.e. E_z, H_z , are known.

Substituting Eqs.(4.10) into Eqs.(4.5) give

$$\frac{\gamma a_3}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \rho \partial \phi} + iw \left(\frac{\mu_\rho}{a_2 \rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi}{a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + iw \mu_z H_z = 0 \quad (11a)$$

$$\frac{iw a_4}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi \partial \rho} - \gamma \left(\frac{\mu_\rho}{a_2 \rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi}{a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} \right) - \gamma \mu_z H_z = 0 \quad (11b)$$

$$\frac{\gamma a_3}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \rho \partial \phi} + iw \left(\frac{\varepsilon_\rho}{a_1 \rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi}{a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + iw \varepsilon_z E_z = 0 \quad (11c)$$

$$\frac{iw a_4}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi \partial \rho} - \gamma \left(\frac{\varepsilon_\rho}{a_1 \rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi}{a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} \right) - \gamma \varepsilon_z E_z = 0 \quad (11d)$$

Where

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{1}{a_2}, \quad a_4 = \frac{\varepsilon_\rho \mu_\phi}{a_1} - \frac{\varepsilon_\phi \mu_\rho}{a_2}$$

Multiplying Eqs.(11a) and (11c) by $\rho/\gamma a_3$, and Eqs.(11b) and (11d) by $\rho/iw a_4$, yield

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \rho \partial \phi} + \frac{iw \rho}{\gamma a_3} \left[\frac{\mu_\rho}{a_2 \rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi}{a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} + \mu_z H_z \right] = 0 \quad (12a)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \rho \partial \rho} - \frac{\rho \gamma}{i w a_4} \left[\frac{\mu_\rho}{a_{2\rho}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi}{a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} + \mu_z H_z \right] \right] = 0 \quad (12b)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \rho \partial \rho} + \frac{i w \rho}{\gamma a_3} \left[\frac{\varepsilon_\rho}{a_{1\rho}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi}{a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} + \varepsilon_z E_z \right] \right] = 0 \quad (12c)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi \partial \phi} - \frac{\rho \gamma}{i w a_4} \left[\frac{\varepsilon_\rho}{a_{1\rho}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi}{a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} + \varepsilon_z E_z \right] \right] = 0 \quad (12d)$$

Subtracting Eq.(4.12b) from (4.12a) gives

$$\left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi a_2}{\mu_\rho a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} + a_2 \frac{\mu_z}{\mu_\rho} H_z \right] \left(\frac{w}{\gamma a_3} - \frac{\gamma}{w a_4} \right) = 0 \quad (13a)$$

Also, subtracting Eq.(4.12d) from (4.12c) yields

$$\left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi a_1}{\varepsilon_\rho a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} + a_1 \frac{\varepsilon_z}{\varepsilon_\rho} E_z \right] \left(\frac{w}{\gamma a_3} - \frac{\gamma}{w a_4} \right) = 0 \quad (13b)$$

It is evident to know $\left(\frac{w}{\gamma a_3} - \frac{\gamma}{w a_4} \right) = w^2 a_4 - \gamma^2 a_3 \neq 0$, hence Eqs.(13) can be reduced to

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\mu_\phi a_2}{\mu_\rho a_1 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 H_z}{\partial \phi^2} + a_2 \frac{\mu_z}{\mu_\rho} H_z = 0 \quad (14a)$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{\varepsilon_\phi a_1}{\varepsilon_\rho a_2 \rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_z}{\partial \phi^2} + a_1 \frac{\varepsilon_z}{\varepsilon_\rho} E_z = 0 \quad (14b)$$

The last equations represent the wave equations for the longitudinal components of the electric

and magnetic fields in cylindrically anisotropic media.

Now, we take $H_z(\rho, \phi) = R(\rho)\Phi(\phi)$ and apply the separation of variables method on Eq.(14a) to obtain

$$\frac{\rho}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial R}{\partial \rho} \right) + a_2 \frac{\mu_z}{\mu_\rho} \rho^2 + \frac{\mu_\phi a_2}{\mu_\rho a_1} \frac{1}{\Phi} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \phi^2} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Eq. (13) can be separated into two ordinary differential equations as

$$\frac{d^2 \Phi_z}{d\phi^2} + v^2 \Phi = 0 \quad v = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (16a)$$

$$\rho^2 \frac{d^2 R}{d\rho^2} + \rho \frac{dR}{d\rho} + [k_\tau^2 \rho^2 - \tau^2] R = 0 \quad (16b)$$

Where

$$k_\tau^2 = \frac{\mu_z a_2}{\mu_\rho}, \tau^2 = \frac{\mu_\phi a_2}{\mu_\rho a_1} v^2$$

The solution to Eq.(16a) is

$$\Phi(\phi) = A_1 e^{iv\phi} + A_2 e^{-iv\phi} \quad (17a)$$

in which v must be an integer to valid the periodic conditions, i.e $\Phi(0) = \Phi(2\pi)$. Eq.(17a) is Bessel's differential equation that has a well-

$$R(\rho) = A_3 J_\tau(k_\tau \rho) + A_4 Y_\tau(k_\tau \rho) \quad (17b)$$

where the two linearly independent solutions in Eq.(17b) are Bessel $J_\tau(k_\tau \rho)$ and Neumann $Y_\tau(k_\tau \rho)$ functions of order τ . Therefore, the

general solution of the longitudinal magnetic field will be

$$H_z(\rho, \varphi, z) = [A_3 J_\tau(k_\tau \rho) + A_4 Y_\tau(k_\tau \rho)] [A_1 e^{iv\varphi} + A_2 e^{-iv\varphi}] e^{-\gamma z} \quad (18a)$$

Using a similar method, Eq.(14b) can be solved to show that the general solution of the longitudinal electric field takes the form

$$E_z(\rho, \varphi, z) = [B_3 J_s(k_s \rho) + B_4 Y_s(k_s \rho)] [B_1 e^{iv\varphi} + B_2 e^{-iv\varphi}] e^{-\gamma z} \quad (18b)$$

in which $k_s^2 = \frac{\epsilon_z a_1}{\epsilon_\rho}, s^2 = \frac{\epsilon_\varphi a_1}{\epsilon_\rho a_2} v^2$.

The parameters A 's and B 's are the region dependent constants that are derived from applying the appropriate boundary conditions. Although the linear combination of exponentials in Eqs.(18) appears to implicate two independent solutions to fully describe the angular variation of the field expressions, the azimuthal periodicity in the cylindrical coordinate system ensures these solutions can be mathematically related to one another. Therefore, for $v \neq 0$, these two azimuthal solutions describe two orthogonal but degenerate modes, in which each may be described by a simple $\cos(v\varphi)$ or $\sin(v\varphi)$ through proper choice of the coordinate system's azimuthal alignment.

One subject of this study determines the dispersion and field relations theoretically of a generally homogeneous and anisotropic circular waveguide. The lined circular-waveguide cross section is presented in Fig.(1) consists of an inner anisotropic core region that is surrounded by an anisotropic cladding region, of radius a and b , respectively, which is embedded in a PEC background medium. In general, each region possesses anisotropic material parameters that are described by diagonal tensors in a cylindrical coordinate system.

Consider the coordinate axis to coincide with the waveguide axis, these take the form $\vec{\epsilon} = \vec{I}(\epsilon_\rho, \epsilon_\varphi, \epsilon_z)\epsilon_0$ and $\vec{\mu} = \vec{I}(\mu_\rho, \mu_\varphi, \mu_z)\mu_0$, in which \vec{I} is the identity dyadic defined as

$$\vec{I} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

To avoid a singularity at $\rho = 0$ in region 1, we take $A_4 = B_4 = 0$ in Eqs.(18) then the longitudinal fields reduce to the form

$$E_{z1}(\rho, \varphi, z) = A J_{s1}(k_{s1} \rho) \cos(v\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (19a)$$

$$H_{z1}(\rho, \varphi, z) = B J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1} \rho) \sin(v\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (19b)$$

Here, k_{s1} and $k_{\tau1}$ are the ρ -directed components of the propagation vectors for electric and magnetic fields, respectively, $k_0 = \omega/c$ is the propagation constants, $s1$ and $\tau1$ are the generally complex orders of the Bessel and Neumann functions, v is the azimuthal mode index.

Figure 1. The Present Waveguide
Source: Atakaramians, et al., (2012)

In region 2, the longitudinal fields will be expressed as

$$E_{z2}(\rho, \varphi, z) = [C_1 J_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) + C_2 Y_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho)] \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (20a)$$

$$H_{z2}(\rho, \varphi, z) = [C_3 J_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) + C_4 Y_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho)] \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (20b)$$

Using the previous definitions, the parameters $k_{si}, k_{\tau i}$ are defined as

$$k_{si} = \sqrt{a_{1i} \frac{\varepsilon_{zi}}{\varepsilon_{\rho i}}} \quad , \quad k_{\tau i} = \sqrt{a_{2i} \frac{\mu_{zi}}{\mu_{\rho i}}} \quad , \quad k_{si} = q_i \sqrt{\frac{a_{1i}}{a_{2i}}} k_{\tau i} \quad (21)$$

where

$$a_{1i} = k_0^2 \varepsilon_{\rho i} \mu_{\varphi i} - \gamma^2 \quad , \quad a_{2i} = k_0^2 \varepsilon_{\varphi i} \mu_{\rho i} - \gamma^2 \quad , \quad q_i = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_{zi} \mu_{\rho i}}{\varepsilon_{\rho i} \mu_{zi}}} \quad (22)$$

Also, the indices $si, \tau i$ will be

$$si = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi i} a_{1i}}{\varepsilon_{\rho i} a_{2i}}} \nu \quad , \quad \tau i = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{\varphi i} a_{2i}}{\mu_{\rho i} a_{1i}}} \nu \quad (23)$$

In region 2, the above expressions can be simplified by applying the PEC condition at $\rho = 0$ on E_{z2} and $E_{\varphi2}$. After manipulation, Eqs.(20) will be

$$E_{z2}(\rho, \varphi, z) = C F_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (24a)$$

$$H_{z2}(\rho, \varphi, z) = D G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (24b)$$

Where

$$F_{s2}(K_{s2}\rho) = J_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) Y_{s2}(k_{s2}b) - J_{s2}(k_{s2}b) Y_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) \quad (25a)$$

$$G_{\tau2}(K_{\tau2}\rho) = J_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) Y'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}b) - J'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}b) Y_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) \quad (25b)$$

The transverse electric and magnetic fields components in each region are determined in term the longitudinal components using Eqs.(10) to get

$$E_{\rho1} = \left[-\frac{\gamma \varepsilon_{z1}}{k_{s1} \varepsilon_{\rho1}} A J'_{s1}(k_{s1}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \nu \varepsilon_{z1} \mu_{\varphi1}}{\rho k_{s1}^2 \varepsilon_{\rho1}} B J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}\rho) \right] \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26a)$$

$$E_{\varphi1} = \left[\frac{\gamma \nu \mu_{z1}}{k_{\tau1}^2 \rho \mu_{\rho1}} A J_{s1}(k_{s1}\rho) + \frac{i \omega \nu \mu_{z1}}{k_{\tau1}} B J'_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}\rho) \right] \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26b)$$

$$E_{\rho2} = \left[-\frac{\gamma \varepsilon_{z2}}{k_{s2} \varepsilon_{\rho2}} C F'_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \nu \varepsilon_{z2} \mu_{\varphi2}}{\rho k_{s2}^2 \varepsilon_{\rho2}} D G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) \right] \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26c)$$

$$E_{\varphi2} = \left[\frac{\gamma \nu \mu_{z2}}{k_{\tau2}^2 \rho \mu_{\rho2}} C F_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) + \frac{i \omega \nu \mu_{z2}}{k_{\tau2}} D G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) \right] \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26d)$$

$$H_{\rho1} = \left[-\frac{\gamma \mu_{z1}}{k_{\tau1}} B J'_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \nu \mu_{z1} \varepsilon_{\varphi1}}{\rho k_{\tau1}^2 \mu_{\rho1}} A J_{s1}(k_{s1}\rho) \right] \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26e)$$

$$H_{\varphi1} = \left[\frac{\gamma \nu}{k_{s1}^2 \rho} B J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \nu \varepsilon_{z1}}{k_{s1}} A J'_{s1}(k_{s1}\rho) \right] \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26f)$$

$$H_{\rho2} = \left[-\frac{\gamma \mu_{z2}}{k_{\tau2}} D G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \nu \mu_{z2} \varepsilon_{\varphi2}}{\rho k_{\tau2}^2 \mu_{\rho2}} C F_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) \right] \sin(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26g)$$

$$H_{\varphi2} = \left[\frac{\gamma \nu}{k_{s2}^2 \rho} D G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) - \frac{i \omega \varepsilon_{z2}}{k_{s2}} C F'_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) \right] \cos(\nu\varphi) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (26h)$$

Where

$$F'_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) = J'_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho)Y_{s2}(k_{s2}b) - J_{s2}(k_{s2}b)Y'_{s2}(k_{s2}\rho) \quad (27a)$$

$$G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) = J'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho)Y'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}b) - J_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}b)Y'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}\rho) \quad (27b)$$

The continuity of the tangential electric and magnetic field components in Eqs.(26) at the interface $\rho = a$ yield the following linear system

$$\varepsilon_{z1}J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)A - \varepsilon_{z2}F_{s2}(k_{s2}a)C = 0$$

$$\mu_{z1}J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)B - \mu_{z2}G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)D = 0$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} \varepsilon_{z1}J_{s1}(k_{s1}a) & 0 & -\varepsilon_{z2}F_{s2}(k_{s2}a) & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_{z1}J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a) & 0 & -\mu_{z2}G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a) \\ \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi1}\mu_{z1}J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{k_{\tau1}^2 a \mu_{\rho1}} & \frac{i\omega\varepsilon_{\varphi1}\mu_{z1}J'_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{\gamma v k_{\tau1}} & \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi2}\mu_{z2}F_{s2}(k_{s2}a)}{k_{\tau2}^2 a \mu_{\rho2}} & \frac{i\omega\varepsilon_{\varphi2}\mu_{z2}G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)}{\gamma v k_{\tau2}} \\ \frac{i\omega\varepsilon_{z1}J'_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{k_{s1}} & \frac{\gamma v J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{k_{s1}^2 a} & \frac{i\omega\varepsilon_{z2}F'_{s2}(k_{s2}a)}{k_{s2}} & \frac{\gamma v G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)}{k_{s2}^2 a} \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

This determinant gives the following dispersion equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\mu_{\varphi1}}{\mu_{\varphi2}} k_{s2} \frac{J'_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)} - \right. \\ & \left. k_{s1} \frac{F'_{s2}(k_{s2}a)}{F_{s2}(k_{s2}a)} \right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi1}}{\varepsilon_{\varphi2}} k_{\tau2} \frac{J'_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)} - k_{\tau1} \frac{G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)}{G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)} \right) \\ & = \frac{\gamma^2 v^2}{a^2 \omega^2} \frac{1}{\mu_{\varphi2} \varepsilon_{\varphi2}} \frac{1}{k_{\tau1} k_{\tau2} k_{s1} k_{s2}} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi2} \mu_{z2}}{\varepsilon_{z2} \mu_{\rho2}} k_{\tau1}^2 - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi1} \mu_{z1}}{\varepsilon_{z1} \mu_{\rho1}} k_{\tau2}^2 \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{\varphi2}}{\mu_{z2}} k_{s1}^2 - \frac{\mu_{\varphi1}}{\mu_{z1}} k_{s2}^2 \right) \quad (29) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (29) represents the dispersion relationship of a cylindrical waveguide with two general anisotropic materials that subject to the conditions

$$\varepsilon_{zi} \neq \varepsilon_{\rho i} \neq \varepsilon_{\varphi i}, \mu_{zi} \neq \mu_{\rho i} \neq \mu_{\varphi i}$$

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi1}\mu_{z1}J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{a\omega\mu_{\rho1}k_{\tau1}^2} A + \frac{i\varepsilon_{\varphi1}\mu_{z1}J'_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{\gamma v k_{\tau1}} B - \frac{\varepsilon_{\varphi2}\mu_{z2}F_{s2}(k_{s2}a)}{a\omega\mu_{\rho2}k_{\tau2}^2} C - \frac{i\mu_{z2}\varepsilon_{\varphi2}G'_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)}{\gamma v k_{\tau2}} D = 0$$

$$\frac{i\varepsilon_{z1}\mu_{\varphi1}J'_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{\gamma v k_{s1}} A - \frac{\gamma v \mu_{\varphi1}J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{\omega k_{s1}^2 a} B - \frac{i\varepsilon_{z2}\mu_{\varphi2}F'_{s2}(k_{s2}a)}{\gamma v k_{s2}} C + \frac{\mu_{\varphi2}G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)}{\omega k_{s2}^2 a} D = 0 \quad (28)$$

For Eqs.(28) to have non-trivial solutions, the determinant of the system must be set to zero. That is;

By using Eqs.(28) and (29), we get the values of the parameters A , B , C and D as the following expressions:

$$B = 1$$

$$C = \frac{\varepsilon_{z1}J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)}{\varepsilon_{z2}F_{s2}(k_{s2}a)} A$$

$$D = \frac{\mu_{z1}J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{\mu_{z2}G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)} B$$

$$A = -\frac{iaw}{\gamma v} \mu_{\rho1} \frac{J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)}{J_{s1}(k_{s1}a)} \frac{\left[\frac{1}{k_{\tau1}J_{\tau1}(k_{\tau1}a)} - \frac{1}{k_{\tau2}\varepsilon_{\varphi1}G_{\tau2}(k_{\tau2}a)} \right]}{\left(\frac{1}{k_{\tau1}^2} - \frac{\mu_{\rho1}\mu_{z2}\varepsilon_{\varphi2}\varepsilon_{z1}}{\mu_{z1}\mu_{\rho2}\varepsilon_{\varphi1}\varepsilon_{z2}k_{\tau2}^2} \right)} B$$

These formulas will be used to define the longitudinal electric and magnetic fields. These formulas were previously derived in detail in chapter three and we decided here not to return the boring details. The difference here is only

represented by the changes in the coefficients $k_{\tau i}, k_{s i}, s i, \tau i$.

Unfortunately, the orders of the Bessel's functions here (represented by $\nu i, \tau i$) are complex numbers. Therefore, solving this equation numerically contains difficulties in order to determine the relationship of the propagation constant with the effective refractive index. These difficulties are dealing with the complex indices of Bessel's functions and how to determine the desired solutions.

In an ordinary isotropic waveguide there are oscillatory and decaying solutions described by Bessel functions with integral order. But the anisotropic nature of the material of the waveguides causes the other kind of solutions. The nature of the modes critically depends on the parameters $k_{\tau 1}, k_{\tau 2}, \nu$. It is well known that when $k_{\tau 1}, k_{\tau 2}$ is imaginary, the modal solutions assume the form of the modified Bessel functions. More importantly, in this case, the anisotropic nature of the waveguide allows the order, ν , of the Bessel function to be fractional and even imaginary (Fathallah, Sakli, & Aguilu, 2015; Shadrivov, Sukhorukov, & Kivshar, 2003), which is not possible in isotropic systems.

In a non-magnetic medium, for example, a propagating *TE* mode with real $k_{\tau 1}, k_{\tau 2}$ implying that $k_0^2 \epsilon_{\rho i} > \gamma^2$ and $k_0^2 \epsilon_{\phi i} > \gamma^2$. If $k_0^2 \epsilon_{\rho i} < \gamma^2$ and $k_0^2 \epsilon_{\phi i} > \gamma^2$, then $\nu^2 < 0$ and the order of the mode becomes imaginary. This is seen to occur in a medium with $\epsilon_{\rho i} < 0$ and $\epsilon_{\phi i} > 0$, whereas in a medium with $\epsilon_{\phi i} = \epsilon_{\rho i}$, this situation would not arise. Note that the inequalities reverse if we research a *TE* mode with imaginary $k_{\tau 1}, k_{\tau 2}$ described by the modified Bessel functions. Physical applications of Bessel functions with imaginary orders have been rarely reported (Xu, et al., 2011). There are consequences to a fractional or imaginary order, ν . The order of the Bessel function and the field distributions now depend on the propagation constant, unlike those for an integral order (m) mode in isotropic media (Waveguides, 2015).

The requirements for an imaginary order for the *TM* modes are actually slightly more involved due to the various possibilities of the material

parameters. There are various kinds of solutions possible that can be presented by changing the sign of the dielectric permittivity components.

Note that, as a special case, for isotropic media, the parameters in Eqs. (21) and (23) will be reduced to the following

$$k_{\tau i} = k_{s i} = k_0^2 \epsilon_i \mu_i - \gamma^2 = k_i, \quad s i = \tau i = \nu$$

Accordingly, the characteristic equation for the isotropic medium ($\epsilon_{z i} = \epsilon_{\rho i} = \epsilon_{\phi i}, \mu_{z i} = \mu_{\rho i} = \mu_{\phi i}$) will be

$$\left(\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2} k_2 \frac{J'_\nu(k_1 a)}{J_\nu(k_1 a)} - k_1 \frac{F'_\nu(k_2 a)}{F_\nu(k_2 a)} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon_1}{\epsilon_2} k_2 \frac{J'_\nu(k_1 a)}{J_\nu(k_1 a)} - k_1 \frac{G'_\nu(k_2 a)}{G_\nu(k_2 a)} \right) = \frac{\gamma^2 \nu^2}{a^2 w^2} \frac{k_1^2 k_2^2}{\mu_2 \epsilon_2} \left(\frac{1}{k_2^2} - \frac{1}{k_1^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{k_2^2} - \frac{1}{k_1^2} \right) \quad (30)$$

Although we used different symbols as necessary, this equation is the same as the one on which the work of chapter three was based.

Effects of Anisotropy on Modes Characteristics

Figs. (2) to (4) represent the relationship between the real part of effective refractive index n_{eff} , the frequency with radius ($a=8$ and 10) μm , and different values of the anisotropy factor η for the modes $LP_{01}, LP_{11}, LP_{12}, LP_{21}, LP_{22}$. The different colors indicate the value of anisotropy factor η , it observed from Fig.(2) which represents the fundamental modes of propagation, Nonlinear increment in the real part of n_{eff} curve with frequency, also it is noticed That all values of real part of n_{eff} curve decreases with increasing the radius. From Figs. (3) and (4) noticed that the other modes have two branches of dispersion curves, This is because the dispersion equation has two different solutions at the same frequency. They are decreased in some frequency ranges with increasing frequency and a raise in other ranges, Also, notice that the modes with higher n_{eff} are referred to as slow modes such as LP_{22}, LP_{12} , and

modes with lower n_{eff} are fast modes such as LP_{11} and LP_{21} .

Figs.(5) to (7) show the real part of n_{eff} as a function of the frequency with the anisotropy factor $\eta = (0.9, 1)$ for modes $LP_{01}, LP_{11}, LP_{12}, LP_{21}, LP_{22}$. Curve's colors indicate the radius $a = (8, 10, 12) \mu m$. We notice that the fundamental modes LP_{01} are forward propagation and the curve decreases with increasing the anisotropy factor η . Other modes form two branches one represent a slow modes

and the other indicates the fast modes. In Figs. (6) and (7) We found that in different frequency ranges below and above the cutoff frequency both the forward and the backward waves can propagate. This is determined by the sign of ϵ_{z1} and ϵ_{t1} for TE modes and by the sign of μ_{z2} and μ_{t2} for TM modes. That is; we approach the zero value of one of the refractive indices. In fact, The increase in radius is physical leads to the greater ability of fields to propagation through the core.

Figure 2. The dispersion curve of mode LP_{01} with $a = (10 \text{ and } 12) \mu m$

Figure 3. The dispersion curve of LP_{11}, LP_{12} mode with $a = (10 \text{ and } 12) \mu m$

Figure 4. The dispersion curve of modes LP_{21} and LP_{22} with $a = (10 \text{ and } 12) \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5. The dispersion curve of mode LP_{01} with $\eta = 0.9$ and 1.1

Figure 6. The dispersion curve of modes LP_{21} and LP_{22} with $\eta = 0.9$ and 1.1

Figure 7. The dispersion curve of modes LP_{21} and LP_{22} with $\eta = 0.9$ and 1.1

Effects of Anisotropy on Modes Spots

Figs.(8) and (9) explains the field distribution as a function of frequency and η factor with $a=10 \mu m$ for LP_{11} and LP_{12} modes respectively in an anisotropic cylindrical metamaterials waveguide, The field distributions are presented using Eqs.(32). notice from the figures that the power at first is high through the cladding and very low through the core with increasing the frequency

vertically and η horizontally, the power in the core begins to increase as the power in the cladding decreases until it is very low. Then we note that the power at the core will decrease. Depending on both powers, we can determine the type of propagation forward or backward at different frequency values. Also, the two figures indicate that the higher the order of mode, the less spot of light.

Figure 8. The variation of LP_{11} mode distribution with frequency and η

Figure 9. The variation of LP_{12} mode distribution with frequency and η

Conclusions

The present work aims to examine the transmission characteristics of electromagnetic waves within cylindrical waveguides which incorporate anisotropic metamaterials. The research yields the following main findings and conclusions:

1. Anisotropic waveguides composed of anisotropic metamaterials exhibit distinct modes characterised by Bessel functions of fractional, imaginary, or complex orders. The observed behavior differs from that of isotropic systems in which the Bessel functions exhibit integral ordering.
2. Propagation behavior in Single Negative (SNG) materials for cylindrical waveguides is characterized by the initiation of all modes with backward propagation. The power flux gradually accumulates until it hits zero at a specific frequency, at which point it propagates forward with a positive power flux. Nevertheless, in anisotropic waveguides, certain higher-order modes display strictly positive or negative power flow, without undergoing any transitions.

3. The significance of the anisotropy factor lies in its crucial role in regulating the propagation characteristics within the cylindrical waveguide. Modifying this coefficient determines the direction of wave propagation and impacts other wave properties.

4. Complexities in Graphical Solutions: During the graphical analysis of wave modes, certain sections of the modes cannot be compressed, resulting in the lack of specific mode properties. This observation implies constraints in the ability to visually or graphically depict specific characteristics of waves.

References

- Atakaramians, S., Argyros, A., Fleming, S., & Kuhlmeier, B. (2012). Hollow-core waveguides with uniaxial metamaterial cladding: Modal equations and guidance conditions. *Optics Society of America*, 29(9), 2462–2477. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAB.29.002462>
- Bhardwaj, A., & et al. (2020). Properties of waveguides filled with anisotropic metamaterials. *C. R. Physique*, 21(5), 485–492. <https://doi.org/10.5802/crphys.39>

- Christensen, J. (2012). Anisotropic metamaterials for full control of acoustic waves. *American Physical Society*, 124301(3), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.85.174301>
- Engheta, N. (2003). Metamaterials with negative permittivity and permeability: Background, salient features, and new trends. *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, 1(6), 187–190.
- Fathallah, W., Sakli, H., & Aguilu, T. (2015). Electromagnetic wave propagation in anisotropic metamaterial waveguides. *Journal of Numerical Modelling*, 28(6), 724–731. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jnm.2054>
- Huang, Y., Lu, W., & Sridhar, S. (2008). Nanowire waveguide made from extremely anisotropic metamaterials. *Physical Review A: Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, 77(6), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.77.063836>
- Mickelson, A. (1993). *Guided Wave Optics*. Van Nostrand Reinhold.
- Mousa, H., & Shabat, M. (2015). Simulation of asymmetry metamaterial waveguide absorber (TE and TM). *Energy Procedia*, 74, 597–607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.652>
- Shadrivov, V., Sukhorukov, A., & Kivshar, Y. (2003). Guided modes in negative-refractive-index waveguides. *Physical Review E*, 67(5), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.67.057602>
- Shen, L., & Wang, Z. (2008). The propagation characteristics in a doubly clad optical fiber including left-handed materials. *Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications*, 22(10), 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156939308783122788>
- Waveguides, S. (2015). Investigation of anisotropic cylindrical metamaterial waveguides. *Elektronika ir Elektrotechnika*, 21(5), 48–53. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.eee.21.5.13345>
- Xu, H., He, Q., Xiao, S., Xi, B., Hao, J., & Zhou, L. (2011). Tight-binding analysis of coupling effects in metamaterials. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 109(2), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3536487>